

Iron Deficiency Anaemia & Ferrum Phosphoricum: A Systematic Review

Dr. Shevanta S. Jadhav^{1*}, Dr. Prerna Tiwari^{2*}, Dr. Kusum Lata^{1*},
Dr. Esha Tyagi^{2*}, Dr. Priya Shete^{1*}, Dr. Jayshree A. Rakh^{1*},
Dr. Rishabh Pandey^{1*}, Dr. Arun B. Jadhav³

¹P.G. Scholars, Department of Practice of Medicine, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Homoeopathic Medical College & Hospital, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

²P.G. Scholars, Department of Materia Medica, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Homoeopathic Medical College & Hospital, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

³Principal, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Homoeopathic Medical College & Hospital, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

*These authors contributed equally to this work.

Corresponding Author: Dr. Kusum Lata

ABSTRACT

Anaemia is defined as a reduced number of red blood cells (RBCs) or less than the normal amount of hemoglobin (Hb) in the blood. Ferrum phosphoricum is a homoeopathic medicine which improves the haemoglobin, in anaemic population. The objective of this review was to assess the effects of Ferrum phosphoricum in anemic patients. Searches were performed using different databases and authentic literatures from year 2000 to till date.

We retrieved 31 studies from the different databases and internet sites searches. After manually removing 08 duplicate studies. Seven reviewers independently screened 23 articles out of which 18 studies were excluded & 05 studies were included in current review by applying modified down and black checklists. The primary reasons for excluding studies were as follows: only abstract articles, in vivo & vitro studies, IDA with other clinical, articles in other languages & not original studies. Limited researches have been done on present topic which requires further researches. There are various literatures available in homoeopathic Materia Medica and repertory but conducted clinical trials are limited. There is not enough evidence to reliably assess the possible role of homeopathy in iron deficiency anaemia. As well as randomized trials, there is a need for observational data to document the different methods of homoeopathic prescribing and how patients respond.

Keywords: Ferrum phosphoricum, Iron deficiency anaemia (IDA), Homoeopathy, Modified down and black checklist, Haemoglobin (Hb).

INTRODUCTION

Anemia is defined as reduced count of red blood cells or less than the normal amount of hemoglobin (Hb) in the blood. It can also be defined as a lowered ability of the blood to carry oxygen.

Iron deficiency anaemia is universal health issue Iron deficiency anaemia is characterized by a defect in haemoglobin synthesis, resulting in hypochromic and

microcytic red blood cells. Iron deficiency can result either due to less nutritional supply, increased demand or blood loss due to any reason. Iron is an important micronutrient which is essential for various functions like cellular growth and differentiation, oxygen binding, transport and storage, enzymatic reactions, immune function, cognitive function, mental and physical growth etc. Hence deficiency of

iron can affect mental and physical growth which leads to decreased in learning capacity and daily activities.

IDA involves population of all age groups and both gender but more common in adolescence girls and pregnant women which leads to serious health problem. Anemia during pregnancy can significantly affect maternal health and increase in perinatal morbidity which is responsible for intra-uterine growth retardation and pre-term delivery. Similarly IDA in adolescent girls affects their physical work capacity and reproductive physiology because of increased iron demand, menstrual blood loss and infections.

According to a World Health Organization (WHO) 53% of all women have anaemia as per the National Family Health Survey 2015-2016 in India. Among this the prevalence of anaemia in adolescent girls (15-19 years) is 56%.

Homeopathy is one of the most widespread and most effective forms of complementary or alternative medicine. Although exact data on the frequency of use of homeopathy in anaemia patients is not available, surveys among general practitioners, indicates that a significant proportion might seek additional advice from homeopaths. The aim of this systematic review was to evaluate whether homeopathic medicine Ferrum phosphoricum have a therapeutic action on the Iron deficiency anemia because no systematic review has yet been done to evaluate the evidence regarding homeopathic treatment strategies in anaemia.

Ferrum phosphoricum is a specific *homeopathic medicine for Anemia* which increases the haemoglobin level and it also break the tendency of low serum ferritin levels in blood. Ferrum phosphoricum attract the oxygen gives tonicity to circular fibers of vessels to contract and thus equalizing the circulation & also has action on intestinal villi to absorb, regulation of bowel movements, utilization of nutrients, micronutrients &

reduction in iron intolerance. Thus Ferrum phosphoricum improve iron absorption from dietary sources or iron supplements and increases haemoglobin levels.

Objectives

The objective of this review was to evaluate the efficacy and effectiveness of homeopathic medicine Ferrum phosphoricum in Iron deficiency anaemia.

METHODS

Search and Selection Criteria

Computerized literature searches were performed to identify all clinical trials (RCT, non RCT), based on homeopathic medicine Ferrum phosphoricum in Iron deficiency anaemia. Databases in present review were MEDLINE, Embase, CINAHL, AMED, PubMed, Google Scholar, Sci-Hub, Clinical Trials. Gov from 2000 to till date. Total 31 studies were searched and out of which only 05 studies fulfilled the selection criteria. The entire material was screened for this review. Furthermore, our own extensive files as well as books on homeopathy and IDA were searched for relevant data. Language used for publication was strictly in English.

Clinical trials of homeopathic medicine Ferrum phosphoricum along with other homeopathic therapeutics with control group were included in this systematic review. Trials with Ferrum phosphoricum as one of several remedies & Ferrum phosphoricum as single remedy, or studies in which Ferrum phosphoricum had been administered concomitantly with other medicines were included.

All studies were read in full by all seven researchers. Data were extracted independently in a standardized, pre-defined fashion (Table 1). Methodological quality of the included trials was assessed using the score according to Modified Methodological Quality checklist developed by Downs & Black, 1998.

SELECTION CRITERIA:-

Inclusion criteria:-

- IDA with homeopathic intervention.

- Both gender of all age groups.
 - Articles based on homoeopathic medicines and IDA of last 18 years.
 - Language strictly English only.
 - All RCT and non RCT based on homoeopathic medicines and IDA containing full text articles was included in the review.
- Exclusion criteria:-**
- IDA with other systemic illness.
 - Case studies.
 - Only abstract.
 - In vivo/vitro studies.
 - Studies on IDA based on other therapies.

Table 1: Summary of Included Review Articles.

Author, Year, Country	Design	Sample, Recruitment, Setting	Intervention	Control	Outcome Measures	Results
PrashantTamboli et.al, 2015, India	Experimental study single blind randomized placebo control trial	Multi stage sampling antenatal care in rural population Recurrence n =60, Setting: Dr. M. L. Dhawale Memorial Homoeopathic Institutes Bhopoli Unit.	Group A-Ferrum phosphoricum &iron supplementation=41 Group B-Placebo & iron supplementation=19	Group A- Ferrum phosphoricum & iron supplementati on group: 41 patients Group B- Placebo & iron supplementati on group: 19 patients. 1 patient from group B was dropped	Hb levels in Pregnant women confirmed with USG in second or third trimester, suffering from mild to moderate anemia with Hb ranging from 7 to 10 gm%.	Ferrum phosph6X decrease the risk of iron deficiency anemia in second & third trimester during pregnancy & sustain the Hb levels in all trimesters without causing any adverse effects.
Dr. ParthAphale 2017,India	Non randomized	n =30, Female patients from age group 17-20 yrs Recruitment : structured interview session Setting: Dr. D.Y. Patil Homoeopathic Medical College & Research Centre, Pune.	Ferrum phosp 3x	No control group	Hb%, Iron level, Reduction in the symptoms.	The statistical analysis proves that Homoeopathy is significantly useful in these 30 cases of Iron Deficiency AnemiaOut of 30 cases 24 cases i.e. 80% showed marked improvement in symptoms. So Ferrum Phos 3X is very much useful in treatment of Iron Deficiency Anemia
Dr. Mamtha A. Gundimi 3 yrs from 2009 to 2012 India.	A quasi experimental pre and post treatment without control group.	30 cases were included by screening test (Hb – 9 to 11 gm %, MCV, MCH, MCHC, Peripheral smear) Patients were follow up for 6 months and the test was repeated after 3 months and 6 months. Setting: Father Muller Homoeopathic Medical College, Mangalore.	Constitutional with different potencies from 30C to 1M depending on patients susceptibility Arsenic album, Calcarea carbonicum, Ferrum met, Ferrum phosphoricum, Phosphorus, Pulsatilla, Lycopodium, Sepia, Natrummuriaticum, Silicea.	No control group	ANOVA test was performed after the study. Conclusion from this study was drawn that constitutional medicines were more effective as compared to constitutional along with lecithin.	It was found that more prevalence in 21 to 30 years of age group, along with female predominance. Most common potency ranged from 200C to 1M. Pulsatilla was most indicated remedy.

Table 1 to be continued...

Dr. S.K. Chaitnaya Nandamudi 2010, India.	Non randomized study.	30 cases were selected based on diagnosis considering Hb% (5-11 gm%), clinical history,, examination. Each case was followed up for 4 months. Setting: Father Muller Homoeopathic Medical College, Mangalore.	Constitutional medicines were prescribed using different potencies ranging from 6C to 1M. Alumina, Ferrum phos, Ferrum met, Silicea, SulphurPuls, Phos, Natmur Stram, Calc c. Cina, Calc p, and Lyco.	No control group	Constitutional remedies were effective in treatment of IDA. Calc Phosph was the most indicated remedy in this study.	Results of the study showed that most of the patients were falling in the age group 8-11 years. Female child was found to be predominant.
Dr. Anita Patil et.al 2014, India.	Randomized Control trial, Open label, parallel group study.	Total 219 girls were screened 9 were excluded due to severe menorrhagia. Where Hb% is less than 12gm% was included in study. Adolescence age group 10-18 years of age. Setting: Bharati VidyapeethKanyaPrashal a, Dhankawadi, Pune 43.	Ferrum phos3x, 4 tabs twice a day along with constitutional medicine.	Group A- Ferrum phosph with Constitutional medicine. Group B-Only Constitutional medicine. Group C- Control group.	Hb%	Constitutional medicine with Ferrum phos has shown improvement in Hb%.

TABLE 2 : Rubrics related to IDA from different repertories :

NAME OF REPERTORY	RUBRICS & SUB RUBRICS MEDICINES
HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICAL REPERTORY BY-ROBIN MURPHY	<p>Clinical - anemia, general abel.abies-c.abrot.absin.Acet-ac.acetan.acon.agar.agn.Alet.aloealst-s.alum.alum-p.alum-sil.alumn.am-c.ambr.anil.ant-c.Ant-t.Apisapoc.aq-mar.Arg-met.Arg-n.Arg-o.Arn.Ars.ars-h.Ars-i.Ars-s-f.aur-ar.bac.bar-c.Bell.ben-d.ben-n.berb.beryl.bism.bol-la.Borx.bov.Bry.cadm-met.Calc.calc-ar.calc-i.calc-lac.Calc-p.calc-sil.calen.calo.camph-br.cann-i.carb-an.Carb-v.Carbn-s.carc.casc.Caust.cean.cedr.cham.Chin.chinin-ar.Chinin-s.chlol.chlor.chloram.chlorpr.cic.cinacob-n.Cocc.coch.coff.colch.coloc.Con.cortico.cortiso.crat.Crot-h.Cupr.cupr-ar.cupr-s.Cycl.dig.eucal.Ferr.ferr-act.Ferr-ar.ferr-br.ferr-c.ferr-cit.Ferr-i.Ferr-m.Ferr-p.ferr-pic.ferr-prox.ferr-s.franz.galeg.Galeo.goss.Graph.Ham.Hell.Helon.hep.Hydr.Ign.iod.ip.Irid-met.Kali-ar.Kali-bi.Kali-br.Kali-c.kali-chl.kali-fcy.kali-hp.kali-m.kali-n.Kali-p.kali-perm.kali-s.kalm.kres.lac-ac.lac-c.lac-d.Lach.lec.lyc.lyss.mag-c.mag-m.Mang.Med.Merc.Merc-c.mez.mill.Mosch.nat-ar.nat-br.Nat-c.nat-cac.nat-hchls.Nat-m.nat-n.Nat-p.Nat-s.nat-aur.Nit-ac.nux-n.Nux-v.ol-j.Olnd.ost.oxyg.paull.peti.petr.Ph-ac.Phos.Phyt.Pic-ac.pitu-a.Plat.Plb.Plb-act.psor.Puls.puls-n.rad-br.rhod.Rhus-t.ric.rob.rub-t.rutasabin.sacch-a.sacch-l.sal-ac.sarr.Sec.Senec.Sep.si.sin-n.sol-ni.spig.Squil.Stann.Staph.stroph-h.stry-af-cit.Sul-ac.sulfa.sulfonam.Sulph.syc.tab.ther.thuj.Thyr.trif-r.trinit.tub.tub-sp.urt-u.ust.valer.vanad.verat.X-rayxan.zinc-zinc-ar.zinc-m.zinc-p.zinc-s.</p> <p>Clinical - anemia, general - iron, deficiency, anemia abies-c.Abrot.Absin.Acet-ac.acetan.Alet.Alum.alum-p.alumn.Am-c.Ambr.Ant-c.Ant-t.aq-mar.Arg-met.arg-n.Ars.ars-i.ars-s-f.aur-ar.bar-c.Bell.bry.cadm-met.Calc.calc-ar.Calc-p.carb-an.Carb-v.Carbn-s.caust.Chin.Chinin-ar.chlor.cinacob-n.Cocc.coch.Con.Cupr.Cycl.dig.Ferr.Ferr-ar.Ferr-i.Ferr-m.Ferr-p.Ferr-s.franz.Graph.Hell.Helon.Hep.ign.Ip.Kali-ar.kali-bi.Kali-c.Kali-fcy.Kali-p.kali-perm.kali-s.lac-c.lach.lec.Lyc.lyss.Mang.Med.merc.Mill.Nat-c.nat-hchls.Nat-m.nat-p.Nit-ac.Nux-v.olnd.Paull.peti.Petr.ph-ac.Phos.phyt.pic-ac.Plat.Plb.Puls.rub-t.sabin.sacch-a.sacch-l.Senec.Sep.Sin-n.Spig.staph.Stry-af-cit.sul-ac.Sulph.thuj.ust.valer.vanad.Xan.zinc.zinc-m.</p> <p>Clinical - anemia, general - iron, deficiency, anemia - alternate days, symptoms, agg. - alum. Clinical - anemia, general - iron, deficiency, anemia - anger, from - ferr.Nux-v. Clinical - anemia, general - iron, deficiency, anemia - emotions, from - ign.nat-m. Clinical - anemia, general - iron, deficiency, anemia - splenic - cean.rub-t. Clinical - anemia, general - iron, deficiency, anemia - winter, in - Ferr. Clinical - anemia, general - malaria, from -alst.Ars.Nat-m.ost.rob. Clinical - anemia, general - menopause period, in - Chin. Clinical - anemia, general - menorrhagia, from - arg-o.ars.Calc.calc-p.Cann-i.chin.crat.Cycl.Ferr.Ferr-p.Graph.Hydr.Kali-c.mang.Nat-m.Puls.sep. Clinical - anemia, general - menstrual, derangements, from-ant-c.arg-o.ars.Bac.calc.calc-p.Cann-i.chin.crat.crot-h.Cycl.ferr.ferr-act.Ferr-p.goss.Graph.ham.helon.Hydr.kali-c.lac-ac.mang.nat-m.Puls.senec.sep.trif-r.xan. Clinical - anemia, general - murmur, in pulmonary artery, with a-ben-d. Clinical - anemia, general - nosebleed, from - am-c.bry.chin.ferr.ferr-act.Ferr-p.hydr.kali-c.Lach.nat-n.Phos.puls. Clinical - anemia, general - nursing, mothers, in- acet-ac.alf.calc-p.Ferr-p.lec. Clinical - anemia, general - nutritional, imbalance, from- acet-ac.alet.alf.alum.Calc-p.chin.Ferr.Ferr-p.helon.nux-v.Thyr. Clinical - anemia, general - pernicious, anemia- Ars.calc.Carc.Crot-h.mang.nat-m.Phos.pic-ac.Thyr.trinit. Clinical - anemia, general - skin, problems, with- kali-m. Clinical - anemia, general - syphilis, from- ars.aur-ar.Calo.crot-h.ferr.mang.med.merc. Clinical - anemia, general - tuberculosis, in- bac. Clinical - anemia, general - young, girls- stroph-h. Clinical - anemia, general - blood loss, anemia, after- ant-c.Arg-o.Ars.Bac.Calc.calc-p.Cann-i.Carb-v.Chin.crat.crot-h.Cycl.Ferr.ferr-act.ferr-p.goss.Graph.ham.Helon.Hydr.ign.kali-c.lac-ac.Lach.mang.nat-br.Nat-m.Nux-v.Ph-ac.Phos.Puls.sabin.senec.sep.staph.Sulph.trif-r.xan. Clinical - anemia, general - menstrual, derangements, from- ant-c.arg-o.ars.Bac.calc.calc-p.Cann-i.chin.crat.crot-h.Cycl.ferr.ferr-act.Ferr-p.goss.Graph.ham.helon.Hydr.kali-c.lac-ac.mang.nat-m.Puls.senec.sep.trif-r.xan.</p>
A SYNOPTIC KEY TO THE MATERIA MEDICA BY- C. M. BOGER	GENERALITIES - Anaemia, chlorosis, etc.-Ars.Calc.calc-p.CHIN.FERR.kali-c.Nat-m.nit-ac.nux-v.Phos.Puls.Sulph.
A CONCISE REPERTORY OF HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICINES BY- DR. S.R. PHATAK	<p>A - Anaemia- ARS.CALC.Calc-p.CHIN.FERR.ferr-ar.Graph.Kali-c.lac-d.lyc.mang.med.nat-c.NAT-M.Nit-ac.Nux-v.Phos.pic-ac.plat.plb.Puls.senec.sep.sul-ac.SULPH.</p> <p>A - Anaemia - grief, from- nat-m.ph-ac.</p> <p>A - Anaemia - haemorrhage, after- Chin.Ferr.</p>

Table 2 to be continued...	
A CLINICAL REPERTORY TO THE DICTIONARY OF MATERIA MEDICA BY- JOHN HENRY CLARK	ANAEMIA. (44)- 1 acet-ac, 1 alet, 1 anil, 1 arg-n, 1 ars, 1 aur-ar, 1 benz-d, 1 calc, 1 calc-p, 1 carb-n-s, 1 casc, 1 chin, 1 chlol, 1 cina, 1 cycl, 1 ferr, 1 ferr-ar, 1 helon, 1 ip, 1 irid, 1 kali-bi, 1 kali-c, 1 kali-p, 1 lac-d, 1 mang, 1 merc, 1 nat-m, 1 nat-n, 1 ol-j, 1 oxyg, 1 petr, 1 pic-ac, 1 plb, 1 puls, 1 rub-t, 1 sil, 1 stann, 1 stroph, 1 sulph, 1 tab, 1 thyr, 1 urt-u, 1 verat
BOGER BOENNINGHAUSEN'S CHARACTERISTICS AND REPERTORY BY- C.M. BOGER	CIRCULATION - Congestions - anaemia- ACON.alum.ANT-T.Arn.ARS.Bell.BRY.CALC.CALC-P.Carbv.Cham.CHIN.CinaCOCC.coff.Coloc.CON.CUPR.cycl.Dig.FERR.GRAPH.Hell.hep.Ign.iod.KALI-C.Lac-d.lach.LYC.mag-c.mag-m.Merc.mez.MOSCH.Nat-c.NAT-M.NIT-AC.nux-m.NUX-V.Ph-ac.PHOS.PLAT.Plb.PULS.rhod.RHUST.rutaSabin.SEP.Sil.spig.SQUIL.stann.STAPH.SULPH.Valer.verat.zinc. CIRCULATION - Palpitation - anaemia in- cycl.dig.eucal.Ferr.hydr.hyper.Kali-c.Natm.ac.Puls.senec.
BOENNINGHAUSEN THERAPEUTIC POCKET BOOK BY- T. F. ALLEN	Blood-ANAEMIA: (59)- 3 ACON, 1 alum, 3 ANT-T, 2 am, 3 ARS, 2 bell, 3 BRY, 3 CALC, 3 CALC-P, 2 carb-v, 2 cham, 3 CHIN, 2 cina, 3 COCH, 1 coff, 2 coloc, 3 CON, 3 CUPR, 1 cycl, 2 dig, 3 FERR, 3 GRAPH, 2 hell, 1 hep, 2 ign, 1 iod, 3 KALI-C, 2 lac-d, 1 kreos, 3 LYC, 1 mag-c, 1 mag-m, 2 merc, 1 mez, 3 MOSCH, 2 nat-c, 3 NAT-M, 3 NIT-AC, 1 nux-m, 3 NUX-V, 3 PHOS, 2 ph-ac, 3 PLAT, 2 plb, 3 PULS, 1 rhod, 3 RHUS-T, 1 ruta, 2 sabin, 3 SQUIL, 3 SEP, 2 sil, 1 spig, 1 stann, 3 STAPH, 3 SULPH, 2 valer, 1 verat, 1 zinc Blood-PALPITATION: ANAEMIA IN: (11)- 1 cycl, 1 dig, 1 eucal, 2 ferr, 1 hydrin-s, 1 hyper, 2 kali-c, 2 nat-m, 1 ph-ac, 2 puls, 1 senec.
COMPLETE REPERTORY BY- ROGER VAN ZANDVOORT	Generals-ANEMIA (226)- 1 abel, 1 abies-c, 1 abrot, 1 absin, 2 acet-ac, 1 acetan, 1 acon, 1 agar, 1 agn, 2 alet, 1 aloe, 1 alst-s, 1 alum, 1 alum-p, 1 alum-sil, 1 alumn, 1 am-c, 1 ambr, 1 anil, 1 ant-c, 2 ant-t, 2 apis, 1 apoc, 1 aq-mar, 2 arg, 2 arg-n, 2 arg-o, 2 am, 3 ARS, 1 ars-h, 2 ars-i, 3 ARS-S-F, 1 aur-ar, 1 bac, 1 bar-c, 2 bell, 1 benz-d, 1 benz-n, 1 beryll, 1 bism, 1 bol, 3 BOR, 1 bov, 2 bry, 1 cadm, 3 CALC, 1 calc-ar, 1 calc-i, 1 calc-l, 3 CALC-P, 1 calc-sil, 1 calen, 1 calo, 1 camph-br, 1 cann-i, 1 carb-an, 2 carb-v, 2 carb-n-s, 1 carc, 1 casc, 2 caust, 1 cean, 1 cedr, 1 cham, 3 CHIN, 1 chin-ar, 2 chin-s, 1 chlol, 1 chlor, 1 chloram, 1 cic, 1 cina, 1 cob-n, 2 cocc, 1 coch, 1 coff, 1 coleh, 1 coloc, 2 con, 1 cortico, 1 cortiso, 1 crat, 2 crot-h, 2 cupr, 1 cupr-ar, 1 cupr-s, 2 cycl, 1 dig, 1 eucal, 3 FERR, 1 ferr-acet, 3 FERR-AR, 1 ferr-br, 1 ferr-c, 1 ferr-cit, 2 ferr-i, 2 ferr-m, 2 ferr-p, 1 ferr-pic, 1 ferr-prox, 1 ferr-s, 1 franz, 1 galeg, 1 goss, 3 GRAPH, 2 ham, 3 HELL, 2 helon, 1 hep, 2 hydr, 2 ign, 1 iod, 1 ip, 2 irid, 3 KALI-AR, 2 kali-bi, 2 kali-br, 2 kali-c, 1 kali-chl, 1 kali-fcy, 1 kali-hp, 1 kali-ma, 1 kali-n, 3 KALI-P, 1 kali-s, 1 kalm, 1 kres, 1 lac-ac, 1 lac-c, 1 lac-d, 2 lach, 1 lec, 1 lyc, 1 lyss, 1 mag-c, 1 mag-m, 3 MANG, 3 MED, 3 MERC, 2 merc-c, 1 merc-k-i, 1 mez, 1 mill, 2 mosch, 1 nat-ar, 1 nat-br, 2 nat-c, 1 nat-cac, 1 nat-hchls, 3 NAT-M, 1 nat-n, 2 nat-p, 2 nat-s, 1 nat-taur, 3 NIT-AC, 1 nux-m, 2 nux-v, 1 ol-j, 2 olnd, 1 ost, 1 oxyg, 1 paull, 1 peti, 1 petr, 2 ph-ac, 3 PHOS, 2 phyt, 2 pic-ac, 1 pitu-a, 3 PLAT, 3 PLB, 2 plb-acet, 1 psor, 3 PULS, 1 puls-n, 1 rad-br, 1 rhod, 2 rhus-t, 1 ric, 1 rob, 1 rub-t, 1 ruta, 1 sabin, 1 sac-alb, 1 sac-l, 1 sal-ac, 1 sarr, 2 sec, 2 senec, 2 sep, 1 sil, 1 sin-n, 1 sol-n, 1 spig, 3 SQUIL, 2 stann, 3 STAPH, 1 stroph, 1 stry-f-c, 3 SUL-AC, 1 sulfa, 1 sulfonam, 3 SULPH, 1 syc-co, 1 tab, 1 ther, 1 thuj, 2 thyr, 1 trif-r, 1 trinit, 1 tub, 1 tub-sp, 1 urt-u, 1 ust, 1 valer, 1 vanad, 1 verat, 2 x-ray, 1 xan, 1 zinc, 1 zinc-ar, 1 zinc-m, 1 zinc-p, 1 zinc-s Generals-ANEMIA blood, from loss of climacteric period, in (1)- 2 chin Generals-ANEMIA blood, from loss of epistaxis, with (10)- 1 am-c, 1 bry, 1 chin, 1 ferr, 1 ferr-acet, 1 hydr, 1 kali-c, 2 lach, 1 nat-n, 1 puls Generals-ANEMIA blood, from loss of hemorrhage, after (19)- 2 arg-o, 2 ars, 2 calc, 2 carb-v, 3 CHIN, 1 crot-h, 3 FERR, 2 helon, 1 hydr, 1 ign, 2 lach, 1 nat-br, 2 nat-m, 2 nux-v, 2 ph-ac, 2 phos, 1 sabin, 1 staph, 2 sulph Generals-ANEMIA blood, from loss of metrorrhagia, menorrhagia, menstrual derangements, from (28)- 1 ant-c, 1 arg-o, 1 ars, 2 bac, 1 calc, 1 calc-p, 2 cann-i, 1 chin, 1 crat, 1 crot-h, 2 cycl, 1 ferr, 1 ferr-acet, 1 goss, 2 graph, 1 ham, 1 helon, 2 hydr, 1 kali-c, 1 lac-ac, 1 mang, 1 nat-m, 1 phos, 2 puls, 1 senec, 1 sep, 1 trif-r, 1 xan Generals- ANEMIA cerebral (4)-1 camph-br, 1 eucal, 1 kali-br, 1 zinc-p Generals-ANEMIA grief, from (2)-1 nat-m, 2 ph-ac Generals-ANEMIA hemolytic malaria, from (5)-1 alst-s, 2 ars, 2 nat-m, 1 ost, 1 rob Generals-ANEMIA hemolytic splenic (1)-1 rub-t Generals-ANEMIA hereditary (1)-1 carc Generals-ANEMIA young girls (1)-1 stroph Generals-ANEMIA impaired production of red blood cells iron deficiency, from, chlorosis (107)- 1 abies-c, 2 abrot, 2 absin, 2 acet-ac, 1 acetan, 2 alet, 2 alum, 1 alum-p, 1 alumn, 2 am-c, 2 ambr, 2 ant-c, 2 ant-t, 1 aq-mar, 2 arg, 1 arg-n, 3 ARS, 1 ars-i, 1 ars-s-f, 1 aur-ar, 1 bar-c, 3 BELL, 1 bry, 1 cadm, 3 CALC, 1 calc-ar, 3 CALC-P, 1 carb-an, 2 carb-v, 3 CARBN-S, 1 caust, 2 chin, 2 chin-ar, 1 chlor, 1 cina, 1 cob-n, 3 COCC, 1 coch, 2 con, 2 cupr, 2 cycl, 1 dig, 3 FERR, 3 FERR-AR, 2 ferr-i, 3 FERR-M, 1 ferr-p, 2 ferr-s, 1 franz, 3 GRAPH, 2 hell, 2 helon, 2 hep, 1 ign, 2 ip, 2 kali-ar, 1 kali-bi, 2 kali-c, 2 kali-fcy, 1 kali-ma, 2 kali-p, 1 kali-s, 1 lac-c, 1 lach, 1 lec, 3 LYC, 2 lyss, 3 MANG, 2 med, 1 merc, 2 mill, 2 nat-c, 1 nat-hchls, 3 NAT-M, 1 nat-p, 3 NIT-AC, 2 nux-v, 1 olnd, 2 paull, 1 peti, 2 petr, 1 ph-ac, 3 PHOS, 1 phyt, 1 pic-ac, 3 PLAT, 2 plb, 3 PULS, 1 rub-t, 1 sabin, 1 sac-alb, 1 sac-l, 3 SENEC, 3 SEP, 2 sin-n, 2 spig, 1 staph, 2 stry-f-c, 1 sul-ac, 3 SULPH, 1 thuj, 1 ust, 1 valer, 1 vanad, 2 xan, 1 zinc, 1 zinc-m Generals-ANEMIA impaired production of red blood cells iron deficiency, from, chlorosis alternate days, sym (1)- 1 alum Generals- ANEMIA impaired production of red blood cells iron deficiency, from, chlorosis anger, from (1)- 2 nux-v Generals-ANEMIA impaired production of red blood cells iron deficiency, from, chlorosis emotions, from (1)- 1 ign Generals- ANEMIA impaired production of red blood cells iron deficiency, from, chlorosis Winter, in (1)- 2 ferr Generals- ANEMIA skin problems, with (1)- 1 kali-m Generals- WEAKNESS, enervation, exhaustion, prostration, infirmity anemia, in (7)- 1 bac, 2 chin, 3 FERR, 3 KALI-C, 2 nat-c, 2 nat-m, 3 PHOS
BOERICKE'S NEW MANUAL OF HOMOEOPATHIC MATERIA MEDICA WITH REPERTORY BY- WILLIAM BOERICKE	Generals- ANEMIA, CHLOROSIS (63)- 2 acet-ac, 3 ALET, 2 alum, 3 ARG-N, 2 am, 3 ARS, 2 bism, 2 calc-ar, 3 CALC, 3 CALC-P, 2 calo, 2 carb-v, 3 CHIN, 2 chin-ar, 3 CHIN-S, 2 cic, 2 con, 2 crot-c, 3 CUPR, 2 cupr-ar, 3 CYCL, 3 FERR-AR, 2 ferr-acet, 3 FERR-I, 3 FERR-MA, 2 ferr-m, 2 ferr-p, 3 GRAPH, 3 HELON, 2 hydr, 2 iod, 2 irid, 2 kali-bi, 3 KALI-C, 2 kali-p, 2 lec, 2 lyc, 3 MANG, 2 merc-s, 2 nat-c, 3 NAT-M, 3 NIT-AC, 2 nux-v, 2 petr, 3 PHOS, 2 phyt, 2 pic-ac, 2 plat, 3 PULS, 3 SEC, 3 SEP, 2 sil, 3 SULPH, 2 zinc-m, 3 ARG-O, 2 calc-l, 2 ferr-red, 2 ferr-cit, 2 zinc-ar, 2 vanad, 2 crat, 2 thyr, 2 goss Generals- ANEMIA, FROM GRIEF (2)-2 nat-m, 3 PH-AC Generals- ANEMIA, FROM MENSTRUAL DERANGEMENTS (13)- 2 ars, 3 CALC, 2 calc-p, 3 CYCL, 3 FERR, 3 GRAPH, 3 KALI-C, 2 mang, 3 NAT-M, 3 PULS, 2 sep, 2 arg-o, 2 crat Generals- ANEMIA, FROM NUTRITIONAL DISTURBANCES (5)-2 alet, 2 alum, 3 CALC-P, 2 ferr, 2 nux-v Generals- ANEMIA, HEMORRHAGIC CHLOROSIS (6)- 3 ARS, 2 calc, 2 crot-c, 2 ign, 3 ARG-O, 2 nat-br
AUGMENTED CLINICAL SYNTHESIS BY- DR.FREDERIK SCHROYENS	GENERALS - ANEMIA - abel.abies-c.Acet-ac.acetan.acon.agar.agn.Alet.aloealst-s.alum.alum-p.alum-sil. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - abortion- alet.carb-v.ferr.ferr-act.kali-c.kali-n.kali-perm.sec.Sep.sulph. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - anemic look- calc-p. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - constipation alum.alumsil.alumn.chin.cycl.ferr.graph.hydr.kali-c.mang.nat-m.nux-v.plb.puls.sulph. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - coryza- bry.chin.ferr.hydr.kali-c.puls. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - emaciation- plb. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - fever and dizziness; asthenic- ferr. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - fever - intermittent- nit-ac. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - genital complaints- cycl. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - gastrointestinal complaints- cycl. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - nervousness-ferr.

	<p>GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - perspiration; profuse- acet-ac. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - pulsation all over the body- kali-c. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - respiration; difficult- acet-ac.calc.stroph-h. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - urinary complaints- cycl. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - urine; copious- acet-ac. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - vertigo- alet.carb-v.chin.crot-h.cycl.eucal.ferr.kali-c.led.phos.senec. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - vomiting- acet-ac. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - Face; red discoloration of- ferr.graph. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - Heart; weak- acet-ac. GENERALS - ANEMIA - accompanied by - Mucous membrane; pale- ferr.graph. GENERALS - ANEMIA - children; in- Calc-p.med. GENERALS - ANEMIA - corpuscles; from reduced red- plb. GENERALS - ANEMIA - disease; from exhausting- acet-ac.alst.Calc-p.Chin.chinin-s.Ferr.helon.kali-c.Nat-m.Ph-ac.Phos.sec. GENERALS - ANEMIA - followed by - blood; loss of- Chin. GENERALS - ANEMIA - girls; in young- alum.tub. GENERALS - ANEMIA - grief; from- nat-m.ph-ac. GENERALS - ANEMIA - heart disease; from- ars.crat.stroph-h. GENERALS - ANEMIA - hemorrhage, after- Arg-o.Ars.bit-ar.Calc.Carb-v.CHIN.crot-h.FERR.Helon.hydr.ign.Lach-nat-br.Nat-m.Nux-v.Ph-ac.Phos.sabin.staph.Sulph. GENERALS - ANEMIA - menorrhagia, from- arg-o.ars.Calc.calc-p.Cann-i.crat.Cycl.Ferr.Graph.helon.Hydr.Kali-c.kalicy.lyss.mang.Nat-m.Phos.Puls.sep. GENERALS - ANEMIA - menses - after- ant-c.calc.chin.ferr.nat-m. GENERALS - ANEMIA - nursing mothers- acet-ac. GENERALS - ANEMIA - nutritional complaints; from- alet.alum.Calc-p.ferr.ferr-p.helon.nux-v. GENERALS - ANEMIA - young people; in- ferr.</p>
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TABLE 3 : Characteristics symptoms of Ferrum phosphoricum related to IDA from different Materia Medica.

SR NO	NAME OF BOOK AND AUTHOR	CHARACTERISTICS OF FERRUM PHOSPHORICUM
1	Dr. Schuessler’s Biochemic System of Medicine	Regarded as the oxygen carrier. Ferrum phos plays a role in the creation of energy in the cells. It gives strength and toughness to the circular walls of blood vessels, especially the arteries. Anemia – loss of vitality, after surgery, radiation. Increases oxygen to the lungs and throughout the body.
2	Pocket Manual of Homoeopathic Materia Medica And Repertory By William Boericke	Anæmic with the false plethora and easy flushing. Ferrum phos. 3x increases hemoglobin.
3	The Encyclopedia of Pure Materia Medica By Timothy F. Allen, A.M., M.D.	At the time of proving following symptoms were noticed: FACE: After moderate tepid bathing, mostly with sponge, lips look blue (seventh day). MOUTH: Light coat on tongue not unusual, but increased, with a yellowish tint increasing towards the base (eighteenth day).
4	Concordant Materia Medica, By Vermeulen Frans	He stated in his proving that Ferrum phosphoricum is the functional agent for tension of the vessel in great doses it can relax the tension of the vessel and therefore create hyperaemia, in small doses on the other hand the relaxed muscles.
5	A Dictionary of Practical Materia Medica, By John Henry Clarke, M.D.	Ferrum phos takes correspond to disturbed states of circulation, irritation, and relaxation of tissue. Inflammation, induration and enlargement of blood vessels; great physical and mental lassitude; indisposed to physical exertion; nervousness, prostration.
6	Lectures on Homœopathic Materia Medica, By James Tyler Kent, A.M., M.D.	Most noticeable features are anaemia and chlorosis, lack of vital heat and false plethora.
7	Physiological Materia Medica By W.H. Burt	Iron has a specific action upon the blood, producing a decrease of the albumin and an increase of water in the serum at the same time diminishing R.B.C.

RESULTS

Search results

We retrieved 31 studies from the different databases and internet site searches. After manually removing 08 duplicate studies. Seven reviewers independently screened 23 articles out of which 18 studies were excluded & 05 studies were included in current review by applying selection criteria (Figure 1). The primary reasons for excluding studies were as follows: only abstract articles, in vivo & vitro studies, IDA with other clinical articles in other languages & not original studies.

Ultimately, two randomized studies & three non-randomized studies were included in the current review.

Figure 1: Flow chart of studies included in this review.

Study characteristics:

Participants

In present review 2 studies were on randomized control trials out of which one study was on antenatal care between second & third trimester which were diagnosed as mild to moderate anemia(Hb%= 7- 10 gm%) & another study participants were adolescents girls age group between 10-18 years with (Hb% = <12gm%) were included. 03 studies were non randomized out of which participants in one study recruited were adolescent age group between 17-20 years & diagnosis was done on the basis of Hb%, Iron level & symptoms of IDA. Second study were conducted on adult age group between 14-60 years included in study after assessing (Hb = 9-11gm%, MCV, MCH, MCHC, Peripheral smear). In third study participants were enrolled only of pediatric age group

between 5-14 years by assessing (Hb%=5-11 gm%), clinical history & examination.

Methodological assessment

Assessment was done by using Modified Methodological Quality Checklist developed by Down and Black, 1998 by summarizing methodological characteristics of all included studies. Modified Methodological Quality Checklist of Downs & Black final score on the quality of 05 included studies ranged from 0 to 9 which includes 2 RCT & 3 Non RCT studies. Scores for each of the five factors devised which varied from 0 to 9 for quality of reporting (maximum score = 11), 0 to 3 for external validity (maximum score = 3), 0 to 5 for internal validity bias (maximum score = 8), 0 to 3 for internal validity confounding (maximum score = 6) and all studies received a 0 for power calculation (maximum score = 1).

Table 4. Modified Downs & Black Checklist Score

Scoring	RCT 1	RCT2	Non RCT 1	Non RCT 2	Non RCT 3	Total
from Q.1-10 for quality of reporting (maximum score = 11)	9	7	9	7	6	38
Q.11 to 13 for external validity (maximum score = 3).	3	3	1	1	2	10
Q.14-20 internal validity bias (maximum score = 8)	6	4	4	2	5	21
Q.21-26 for internal validity confounding (maximum score = 6)	3	2	3	2	2	12
Q.27. power maximum score 1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	21	16	17	12	15	81

Figure 2. Risk of bias assessment based on Modified Downs & Black Checklist

DISCUSSION

After searching so many databases total 31 researches were found. Out of which only 05 studies were included in present review. Methodological quality of the included trials was assessed by using modified down and black checklists.

The two randomized controlled trials showed the effectiveness of Ferrum phosphoricum in iron deficiency anaemia where one of the study showed that Ferrum Phosphoricum 6X decreases the risk of iron deficiency anaemia in second & third trimester during pregnancy & sustain the Hb levels throughout the pregnancy without causing any adverse effects. Second study was conducted on adolescence girls revealed that constitutional medicine along with Ferrum phosphoricum has capacity to increase Hb level in Iron deficiency anaemia. This review also included three non RCT suggesting that the effectiveness of a standardized homeopathic medicine Ferrum phosphoricum is capable of improving the Hb levels in iron deficiency anaemia. Insufficient data is available on Ferrum phosphoricum in IDA, so further studies are required to see the effectiveness of Ferrum Phosphoricum.

CONCLUSION

The result indicates that there was increase in haemoglobin levels in cases of IDA patients. Therefore it can be concluded that the homeopathic medicine Ferrum phosphoricum may have beneficial effect in improving the Hb level in IDA patients. Therefore it is a good choice as specific remedy for IDA. Since limited researches have been done on present topic which requires further researches.

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Conflict Of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

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